

Identification, Isolation, and Antibiotic Susceptibility of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from *Hyalomma* Species that Infest Cows in Iraq's Wasit Province

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Abstract

Several *Hyalomma* species have been isolated and identified in Iraq, including *Hyalomma truncatum*, which was initially discovered in Najaf province, and *Hyalomma asiaticum*, which was discovered in Duhok. There are also known to be other species, like *Hyalomma anatolicum*, which is a major vector for diseases like theileriosis. These ticks are known to spread diseases, including Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever (CCHF), and are found on a variety of species, such as cattle, sheep, and camels. It not only spreads theileria disease but also carries *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which is resistant to many antibiotics like amikacin (AK), amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (AMC), ceftriaxone (C), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (TMP), cefotaxime (CTX), N-acetylcysteine (NA), meropenem (MEM), azithromycin (ATM), gentamicin (CN), and rifampicin (RA). The 100 ticks that were removed from 20 cows were identified as *Hyalomma* spp., and they were either males (64%, n = 64) or nymphs (36 %, n = 36). Gram staining was performed on 45 distinct bacterial species that were isolated from the ticks that were collected. The findings indicated that 18 distinct bacterial species are represented among the bacterial isolates. Of the total isolates, about 62.2% (n = 28) were found to be distinct gram-positive bacterial species. In total, 37.7% (n = 17) of the isolates of various species were gram-negative bacteria. Using the VITEK®2 technology, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was isolated and diagnosed with a 95% diagnostic rate

Keywords: *P. aeruginosa*, *Hyalomma* spp., Wasit, Antimicrobial resistance, VITEK®2 technology.

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Introduction

Emergence of pathogens and vectors in new hosts and new geographical areas poses great threats for public and veterinary health. Ticks are responsible for the spread of numerous pathogens worldwide and species belonging to the genus *Hyalomma* have been shown to have a particular epidemiological role

(Hubálek et al., 2020; EstradaPeña et al., 2021). About 900 species of ticks are spread throughout the world (De la Fuente et al., 2017) and they are the main carrier of pathogenic microorganisms for animals and humans in the Northern Hemisphere, and they are also the main carrier of pathogenic microorganisms for animals in the Southern Hemisphere (Eisen & Eisen, 2018). Ticks are important ectoparasites, that parasitize birds, reptiles, and mammals in particular, so they are of great medical and veterinary importance (Mehlhorn, 2004) and transmit types of bacteria, protozoa, rickettsia, and viruses that infect humans and animals and cause several diseases (Ullah et al., 2020). *Hyalomma* species are distributed on the continents of Asia, Africa, and Europe (Sands et al., 2017). There are twenty-seven *Hyalomma* species. (Guglielmone et al., 2010). The genus *Hyalomma* has three life cycle stages: larvae, nymphs and adults, each stage requiring only one blood meal. Adults usually feed on large vertebrate animals, especially livestock, while larvae and nymphs prefer small animals in hidden places (Kar et al., 2020; Madison-Antenucci et al., 2020; Sonenshine, 2018). Ticks are mostly responsible for the significant losses they generate because they can spread diseases to livestock, which are extremely valuable to the global economy. Moreover, tick bites lower the quality of hides, and their blood sucking causes anemia and weight loss in cattle. (Desta, 2016).

In recent years, many cases of infection with CCHF disease, which is transmitted by the genus *Hyalomma*, have been recorded, especially in Wasit governorate in southern Iraq, where migratory birds spread. The possibility of this disease spreading to other countries through migratory birds that carry this disease has been reported. The type of tick is very high. Some microorganisms are life threatening to animals and humans like *P. aeruginosa*. Gram-negative, aerobic, motile, and somewhat curved, *P. aeruginosa* is a common bacterium found in a variety of settings, such as soil, water, air, and the tissues of plants and animals. Well-known for being an opportunistic human pathogen, *P. aeruginosa* can cause a wide range of serious acute and chronic infections that can be fatal, including pneumonia, otitis media, meningitis, and urinary tract infections. The ability of *P. aeruginosa* to secrete extracellular enzymes (Cross et al., 1983). However, a few virulent characteristics, the ability to build biofilms, and resistance to antibiotics make *P. aeruginosa* a harmful microbe. Additionally, the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria brought on by antibiotic abuse and overuse raises morbidity and mortality rates in patients with impaired immune systems. Finding safe, healthy, and natural substitute antimicrobial agents is crucial for these reasons. Our ultimate objective is to incorporate preventative strategies and antibiotic resistance in this review (Li et al., 2023). The present study aims to isolate and identify *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from the cow's tick *Hyalomma spp.* in Wasit province in Iraq. Furthermore, our objective is to ascertain whether the isolated bacterial species exhibit resistance to antimicrobial drugs that are clinically relevant. This is the first study that looks into the hard tick's potential function as an AMR bacterial reservoir in our area, as far as we are aware.

Aim of the Study

1. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolation and identification from *Hyalomma* species.
2. Examine the degree of *P. aeruginosa* resistance to specific antibiotics.

Materials and Methods

Research Area

The current study used hard ticks collected from cows throughout Wasit province in the southern part of Iraq. The wasit region is one of the most fertile regions in Iraq as a soil and water treasure. In addition, it has a suitable atmosphere. Wasit governorate is characterized by a desert climate. It is in the semi-tropical region and is characterized by high temperatures and a level of dryness in the summer and moderate temperatures in the winter. As for rainfall, it is characterized by scarcity and fluctuation, and its amounts increase in the eastern parts of the governorate, where its amounts range between 150 and 300

mm. The area is now suitable for growing a variety of crops because of these factors. As a result, most of the economic activity in the Wasit governorate is focused on agriculture. Due to the region's abundance of agricultural resources, the livestock industry has grown. There were about 481350 cows in the Wasit area in 2005. These elements, along with the abundance of animals and the regularity of human-animal contact, made the area appropriate for our research.

The Process of Tick Collecting and Identification

A total of 100 ticks were removed from 20 female cows in Wasit, Iraq, in May 2025. After being collected, the ticks were taken to the lab for additional examination and kept in a jar with 70% ethanol.

Separating Bacteria from Ticks

After being cleaned with 70% ethanol, the ticks were rinsed three times with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). The internal organs of Tick were sliced into tiny pieces and then placed into tubes after the exoskeletons were removed using sterile forceps and blades. After inoculating each homogenate into 3 ml of nutritional broth media in a 15 ml tube, the mixture was shaken at 250 rpm for 24 hours at 37°C (Jalil & Zenad. 2016; Aljasham et al., 2023) A wide variety of bacteria were able to thrive by plating the developing cultures into various media, such as MacConkey agar and blood agar base. Based on morphology (color, structure, form, and size), one or two colonies were chosen from each plate following a 24-hour incubation period at 37°C. The bacterial isolates were stored with glycerol at -80°C for further analysis.

Detection of the Isolates

Based on biochemical and morphological tests and matching them with the results described by Holt et al. (1994) and according to API 20 E confirmatory test.

Identification of *Providencia spp.* by VITEK®2 Compact System

Aseptically, pure colonies were transferred into a polystyrene tube containing saline NaCl to a density equivalent to a McFarland tube number 0.5 ($1-1.5 \times 10^8$ CFU/ml); the density was determined using a VITEK®2 Densi Chek spectrophotometer. Then the tube and card were put into the VITEK®2 cassette, and the card was auto inoculated inside the VITEK®2 instrument by a procedure dependent on vacuum release. Wells in the card were easily noticed, scanned, and read every 15 minutes, with a total numeral of incubation time which about eight hours. The VITEK®2 Compact system is used to confirm the isolates.

Antibiotic Ten Test (Qualitative Disk Method)

Twelve antibiotic disks (amikacin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ceftriaxone, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, cefotaximase, N-acetyl cysteine, meropenem, azithromycin, gentamicin, and rifampicin) were employed in accordance with the previously established procedure to determine the sensitivity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates (Bauer, 1966).

Result

Identification of the Isolated Bacteria

The 100 ticks that were taken from 20 cows were identified as *Hyalomma spp.*, and they were divided into males (36 %, n = 36) and nymphs (64%, n = 64). A total of 45 bacterial species were isolated from the ticks that were collected and then put through the Gram staining process. followed by the VITEK®2 Compact system's identity. According to the findings, the isolated bacteria are members of eighteen distinct bacterial species. Of all the isolates, about 62.2% (n = 28) were found to be distinct species of

gram-positive bacteria. 37.7% (n = 17) of the total isolates of various species were gram-negative bacteria, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (n = 5).

In order to isolate the bacteria *P. aeruginosa*, the primary goal of the tick collection was to isolate the isolates based on the phenotypic characteristics of the developing colonies. These included the colonies' dark appearance and the clear halo that surrounded the center of the blood agars, which indicated that they could decompose blood, as well as the colonies' pale color, inability to ferment the sugar lactose located in the center of the plant, and smell similar to fermented grapes. Oxidase test findings were positive, according to the biochemical test results. Each isolate was identified by its incapacity to generate hydrogen sulfide gas and its failure to ferment lactose and sugar. For the detection of Enterobacteriaceae, the API 20 E confirmatory was utilized. Table 1 and Figure 1 demonstrate the results, which reveal that *P. aeruginosa* was the tested isolate.

Table 1. API20E Technique of *P.aeruginosa*

No.	Active ingredients	Symbol test	Results
1.	Ortho NitroPhenyl-Bd-Galactopyranside	ONPG	-
2.	L-arginine	ADH	+
3.	L-Lysine	LDC	-
4.	L-Ornithin	ODC	+
5.	Trisodium citrate	CIT	-
6.	Sodium thiosulfate	H ₂ S	-
7.	Urea	URE	-
8.	L-tryptophane	TDA	-
9.	L-tryptophane (indole production)	IND	-
10.	Sodium pyruvate	VP	+
11.	Gelatin (bovine origin)	GEL	+
12.	D-Glucose	GLU	-
13.	D-Mannitol	MAN	-
14.	Inositol	INO	+
15.	D-Sorbitol	SOR	-
16.	L-Rhamnose	RHA	-
17.	D-Saccharose (sucrose)	SAC	-
18.	D-Melibiose	MEL	+
19.	Amygdaline	AMY	-
20.	L-Arabinose	ARA	-

Figure 1. API20 E Technique for *P.aeruginosa*

P.aeruginosa was diagnosed using the VITEK®2 Compact system, as shown in Table 2 and Figure 2. Colonies that have grown on plate medium can be tested for the production of cytochrome oxidase by adding the oxidase test reagent or test strip. When violet appears, the test is positive.

Table 2. VITEK®2 Compact System Technique Used for Identification of *P.aeruginosa*

Well No	Test	Symbol	Result of Cow
2	Ala-Pro-Arylamidase	APPA	+
3	Adonitol	ADO	-
4	L-Pyrrolydonyl-Arylamidase	PyrA	-
5	L- Arabitol	LARL	-
7	D – Cellobiose	dCEL	-
9	Beta- Galactosidase	BGAL	-
10	H ₂ S Production	H ₂ S	-
11	Beta – N -Acety -Glucosamindase	BNAG	-
12	Glutamyl Arylamidase pNA	AGLTp	+
13	D - Glucose	dGLU	+
14	Gamma - Glutamyl-Tresferase	GGT	+
15	Fermentation/Glucose	OFF	-
17	Bate – Glucosidase	BGLU	-
18	D – Maltose	dMAL	-
19	D – Mannitol	dMAN	-
20	D – Mannose	dMNE	+
21	Beta – Xylosidase	BXYL	-
22	Beta -Alanine Arylamidase pNA	BAlap	+
23	L– Prolin arylamidaes	ProA	+
26	Lipase	LIP	-
27	Palatinose	PLE	-
29	Tyrosine Arylamidase	TyrA	-
31	Urease	URE	-
32	D –Sorbitol	dSOR	-
33	Saccharose/ Sucrose	SAC	-
34	D-Tagatose	dTAG	-
35	D – Trehalose	dTER	-
36	Citrate(sodium)	CIT	+
37	Malonate	MNT	+
39	5 – KETO –D -Gluconate	5KG	-
40	L –Lactate alkanisation	ILATK	+
41	Alpha - Glucosidase	AGLU	-
42	Succinate alkanisation	SUCT	+
43	Beta – N – Acetyl -Galactosaminidase	NAGA	-
44	Alpha Galactosidase	AGAL	-
45	Phosphatase	PHOS	-
46	Glycin arylamidas	Gly A	-
47	Ornithine decarboxylase	ODC	-
48	Lysine decarboxylase	LDC	-
53	L – Histidine assimilation	IHISa	+
56	Coumarate	CMT	+
57	Beta – Glucuronidase	BGUR	-
58	O /129 resistance (comp.vibro)	O129 R	+
59	Glu – Glu Arg Aryamidas	GGAA	-
61	L – Malate assimilation	IMLTa	+
62	Ellman	ELLM	-
64	L – Lactate assimilation	ILATa	+

Patient Name: abdullah 2 ,		Patient ID: abdullah 2															
Location:		Physician:															
Lab ID: abdufah 2		Isolate Number: 1															
Organism Quantity:																	
Selected Organism : Pseudomonas aeruginosa																	
Source: 2		Collected:															
Comments:																	
Identification Information		Analysis Time: 6.78 hours	Status: Final														
Selected Organism		95% Probability	Pseudomonas aeruginosa														
ID Analysis Messages		Bionumber:	1043051003500352														
Biochemical Details																	
2	APPA	+	3	ADO	-	4	PyrA	-	5	IARL	-	7	dCEL	-	9	BGAL	-
10	H2S	-	11	BNAG	-	12	AGLTp	+	13	dGLU	+	14	GGT	+	15	OFF	-
17	BGLU	-	18	dMAL	-	19	dMAN	-	20	dMNE	+	21	BXYL	-	22	BAlap	+
23	ProA	+	26	LIP	-	27	PLE	-	29	TyrA	-	31	URE	-	32	dSOR	-
33	SAC	-	34	dTAG	-	35	dTRE	-	36	CIT	+	37	MNT	+	39	SKG	-
40	ILATk	+	41	AGLU	-	42	SUCT	+	43	NAGA	-	44	AGAL	-	45	PHOS	-
46	GlyA	-	47	ODC	-	48	LDC	-	53	IHISa	+	56	CMT	+	57	BGUR	-
58	O129R	+	59	GGAA	-	61	MLTa	+	62	ELLM	-	64	ILATa	+			

Figure 2. VITEK®2 Compact System Results that Confirmed *P.aeruginosa*

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

The results of the antibiotic susceptibility test are shown in Table 3. The antibiotic was selected to treat certain *P. aeruginosa* infections. The table displays the test findings together with the bacteria's resistance and allergy to the antibiotic. Regarding the antibiotic tablet, compare it to the CLSI 2019 standard tables to ascertain the degree of bacterial resistance to the antibiotics employed and the severity of that resistance, which spans a broad range of medications. The findings on the impact of antibiotic samples on *P.aeruginosa* bacteria (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Antibiotic Sensitivity Pattern has been Determined by the Zone

Table 3. Result of Resistant and Sensitive of Antibiotics of *P.Aeruginosa*

No.	Antibiotic	Result
1	(AK)	Resistant
2	(AMC)	Resistant
3	(C)	Resistant
4	(TMP)	Resistant
5	(CTX)	Resistant
6	(NA)	Resistant
7	(MEM)	Resistant
8	(ATM)	Resistant
9	(CN)	Resistant
10	(RA)	Resistant

The increasing prevalence of AMR bacteria is a global concern affecting both animal and human health. We do not fully understand the role of ticks in disseminating AMR bacteria. To address this issue, different bacteria were isolated from ticks from wasit province, and their antimicrobial susceptibilities to different clinically utilized antimicrobials were determined. We concluded that isolated bacteria from ticks showed significant resistance to different antimicrobial agents, including amikacin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ceftriaxone, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, cefotaximase, N-acetyl cysteine, meropenem, azithromycin, gentamicin, and rifampicin. Collectively, these data indicate the existence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in these bacteria within the ticks that needs further research impetus. The prevalence of multidrug resistance (MDR) was 100%; the multidrug antibiotic resistance index (MARI) was also 1, suggesting extreme multidrug resistance (see Table 4).

Table 4. Percentage of Resistant and Susceptible Isolates of *P.aeruginosa* to Antibiotics

Antibiotic	Resistance	Sensitive
AK	53.3%	46.6%
AMC	93.3%	6.6%
C	60%	40%
TMP	100%	-
CTX	100%	-
NA	80%	20%
MEM	73.4%	26.6%
ATM	66.6%	33.3%
CN	66.6%	33.3%
RA	100%	-

Discussion

Moreover, practically every isolated bacterial species can infect and transfer from animals to people, leading to issues with both health and the economy. This is the first report that we are aware of in the area about ticks and their connection to AMR bacteria in Iraq. *Staphylococcus*, *Enterococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Klebsiella*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Stenotrophomonas* are among the genera of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria that we identified during our investigation, and the results of other studies are consistent with these findings. (Wei et al., 2022; Zhuang et al., 2014). It's possible that ticks serve as reservoir hosts for harmful germs, which could endanger both human and animal health. To reducing possible zoonotic effects, other tick species might be checked for AMR bacteria. The investigation of antimicrobial-resistant genes (ARGs) against the tested antimicrobial drugs requires more study. The resistance traits that have been discovered are alarming and provide evidence for ticks' active function as AMR bacterial carriers.

The degree of resistance and the use of antibiotics are already directly correlated, according to scientific studies. (Goossens et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, more research is needed to look at the relationship between tick antibiotic use, ARGs, and microbiota. In areas where tick-borne illnesses are common and antimicrobial use is widespread, monitoring efforts need to be strengthened. As demonstrated by our findings, ticks may serve as a vector for the spread of several AMR bacteria. The involvement of ticks in the spread and transmission of AMR bacteria among many hosts, such as humans, animals, and the environment, requires more research to fully address these issues. Environmental factors and blood feeds may have an impact on tick microbiome. (Thapa et al., 2019; Sweil & Kwan. 2017). Numerous species of bacterial genera, including *Staphylococcus* and *Pseudomonas*, are found in the environment. We discovered these bacterial species in ticks, which may indicate that the ticks picked up these bacteria from their surroundings. These bacterial genera have also been found in ticks in earlier investigations. Nevertheless, there is ongoing discussion regarding whether these bacteria are part of the tick microbiota or are merely environmental pollutants (Li et al., 2022; Narasimhan et al., 2021). Ticks and their hosts can spread AMR bacteria more easily thanks to the tick-host relationship. (Dennis & Piesman. 2005). In another study, this bacterium was also found to be resistant to meropenem and amikacin (Khan & Faiz. 2016). In 2018, ceftazidime, cefixime, ceftriaxone, and cefepime resistance rates were 81%, 10.03%, 75.99%, and 86.04%, respectively. In 2022, these rates increased significantly to 91.07%, 9.92%, 90.98, and 90.09, while resistance rates in carbapenems between imipenem and meropenem increased as well (Hameed. 2023). Also, out of the 92 isolates, 26 (28.2%) were found to be multidrug resistant (MDR); 21 (22.7%) were classified as extremely drug resistant (XDR). Highest resistance rate was found for gatifloxacin (42%) while ciprofloxacin accounted for the antibiotic with the lowest resistance rate (2%) (González-Olvera et al., 2019). Results showed that 53% out of *P. aeruginosa* isolates exhibited MDR pattern *P. aeruginosa* isolates showed higher resistance to ciprofloxacin, gatifloxacin and meropenem and intermediate resistance to cefoperazone, cefepime, piperacillin, tobramycin, piperacillin-tazobactam, ceftazidime and aztreonam while Low bacterial resistance was noted against colistin only (Mohamed & Abdelhamid. 2020).

Multi-drug-resistant isolates of Abd et al. were chosen based on their resistance pattern, and their minimum inhibitory concentrations for amikacin, gentamicin, ceftazidime, and ciprofloxacin were determined through testing. Amikacin had the lowest minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) when compared to other combinations. The combination of amikacin and β -lactam antibiotics was found to be the most effective. The results indicated that EDTA makes antibiotics more effective against *P. aeruginosa* isolates, particularly when combined with aminoglycoside antibiotics (Abd et al., 2011). Our results are also consistent with Aljashaam et al., who found that the isolated bacteria were resistant to many antibiotics (Aljasham et al., 2023). Several bacteria that were discovered throughout our investigation may be pathogens. But we also found several species of *Pseudomonas*, including *P. aeruginosa*, which may be a component of the tick's microbiome. Since *Pseudomonas* species are resistant to several kinds of antimicrobial drugs, it is possible that they were obtained from other hosts or habitats. Different bacteria found in ticks along with varying resistance patterns may suggest that these AMR bacteria are actively spreading from ticks to their hosts. To find out how ticks contribute to the spread of AMR bacteria to both humans and animals, more research should be promoted.

Conclusion

The danger of cow ticks serving as a reservoir for AMR bacteria was brought to light by our investigation. AMR bacteria can spread from cows to humans and other animals through ticks, which poses a serious risk to public health. This research will raise awareness of tick-transmitted pathogens that endanger human and animal health and provide a basis for future studies on AMR pathogens.

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